

Sars-Cov - 2 and genetic mutation MTHFR C667T-A1298C

Whatever the genetic mutation diagnosed, what is essential for you, to know, understand, how to feed yourself, how to detoxify to achieve a better state of Health and ward off the ailments that you have not been able to send away for a long time, by any means you have tried. Believe me it is very important that you understand to live longer. When you have mutations of the MTHFR gene, you will need special help.

Have one or both of the genes C677T and/or A1298C, it means that it is time to act in a positive way to help yourself, to support your body and prevent the serious health problems that lurk behind these two series of numbers are the most studied among the many, which are related to health problems, but also to various diseases, serious. In all these years of absolute silence, since the discovery of this genetic mutation MTHFR, following the Human Genome Project (HGP, acronym for Human Genome Project) 1988-2003, no one has been told how important it is on our health through nutrition. This mutation is inherited from parents, for generations, all over the world. The vast majority of people and even professionals, have never considered a full title, or better to say, they knew in a few, and it was considered only to the version of the folic acid for pregnant women and homocysteine, indicating the integration of folate that had not taken on the enzyme MTHFR, in a few words, as in food, the vitamin does not arrive at its final destination of conversion, since it is not in the active that our body can use, creating a block chain for the state of health, to the "Mutant Genetic" equal to 40 - 60 % of the world's population.

People have been recommended intakes of medicines, supplements, and for some people could go well, but not for others, yet we continue to prescribe medicines, and that the same prey on vitamins linked to the Genetic mutation MTHFR, already precarious, and missing, causing traffic delays or blockages in the process of conversion of the enzyme MTHFR, as well as in the cases of supplements of folate simple, non-active, by activating a process called block of the cycle of Methylation, while keeping all overnight sick. Nature, the creator has given us everything, but it is a pity that it is often used badly and only for the profit of a few, but potentially our body has everything to repair itself, provided that the right elements come to it.

In a nutshell, every time we feed, we do it or we are proposed to do it, through supplements or diets, without knowing what we really manage to use to convert according to our genetic nature inherited from parents, in order to create the energies to live. People do not have the awareness of what is necessary to feed us properly, and clearly without doing other harm. This should also know people who have studied the matter, but then why do people get sick more and more, putting aside the toxicity of environmental and food interests, because until now, in all these years, the importance of the genetic mutation MTHFR and not only that this has been overlooked, perhaps because they knew that feeding well the motor, the people would have been better, and in being the best also means to better understand and be more transparent with the mind and energetic.

Because you see, even though we physically might feel better physically, it will always be the mind and gut driving the whole thing. When knowledge and culture is not complete, here the mind deceives us by making us do, share things in negative realities, for lack of stored news or false truths. At this point, it is shown the existence of a big problem, that can put you in serious risk people, to develop additional problems, because of the integration is not valid, a power supply the wrong specification or a diet that is not suitable, according to the information and misperceptions, to the detriment of real personal dictated by our true condition, constitutional, genetic, masking many other problems connected or connectable.

- Amino acid and mineral imbalances
- Detoxification problems
- Heavy metal toxicity
- Homocysteine imbalances
- Problems with methylation

Any other symptoms associated with MTHFR

Chronic disease

Disease prevention

Physical pain

If we are bad it is also for the lack of knowledge, for the lack of information, always held back by interests of various kinds. Therefore, nutrition is essential for our health, as long as we follow the constitutional predispositions, given the possibility of being able to know them genetically. By observing these symptoms, we might find ourselves in such conditions, and thus be “candied” to have the genetic mutation. It can be certified with a simple genetic test in many laboratories, or the first to follow a path of non-invasive, to assess the status of health food, nutritional, toxicological, and functional, performing the mineralogramma designed for this occasion, called B-Byron, to observe, the percentage of the functioning of MTHFR, the presence of heavy metals, the state of our immune system and of all the vitamins, having a framework of clearly directs us to the correct nutrition according to our personal nature, for we are what we eat.

These notions were well detailed and described in two books basic that of Dr. Andrew Rostenberg “Your Genius Body” 2018 your body is brilliant, and that of Dr. Maurizio Proietti, Pollution, and disease” in 2018, hitting every detail of what I have experienced personally. Since 1988, when I began to study and do research, in the various sectors related to each other, starting from a new mode of reading, with natural mathematical medicine, until today also demonstrating the correlations with the SARS-Cov-2 virus 2019 and the genetic mutation MTHFR.

Let's look at the positive side of having inherited mutations

If you are discovered to have mutations in the gene MTHFR at first glance it may be a bit of a shock, to know of this condition in our DNA, but the positive side and just to know it with certainty, that allows us to establish a plan of action to mitigate further damage, providing the body with the mind and the news and the substances it needs, so that they may produce relief of symptoms, but also to prevent diseases associated with mutations. Knowing our genes in advance is a predictive advantage for our psychophysical well-being. The natural mathematical path can make a difference to your life and your health.

How to treat MTHFR

People who discover for the first time that they possess by Epigenetic transmission, from parents to children, the genetic mutation MTHFR, comes the terrible question “and now, what should I do?”.

Most of the time he is advised to take the “folates ” immediately, yes but which folate ? and here you are already in error as a result of the various conditions to be evaluated. In fact, mutations of the MTHFR gene affect people in different ways, so it is important to understand how to treat dialogue at the level of verbal communication, in the right way, in short, you will have to have cultural skills of social psychology, as well as nutrition, since there is the right and the wrong way.

Treat MTHFR appropriately

There are many other issues that need to be evaluated before optimizing one's state of well-being. The first step is cultural, to inform in a clear and understandable way of what the MTHFR is, in essence we can compare it to a car that no longer arrives the gasoline well, and the Pistons move late limping, attract more and more slags and not be able to eliminate them, not arriving all right. The second thing is the organization of the right nutritional path, since not being able to convert folates and methionine, but all foods contain methionine. Fortunately in different quantities and here comes the mathematical game of nutrition through the reading of food colors, non-invasive and completely natural, to balance physical and mental imbalances, also carrying out prevention.

The people who have the genetic disorder MTHFR, 't know they have always been, which is not shown symptoms if, even if it shows them in time with bad health states, incomprehensible beds with the medical classic these are often passed to anorexic, exhausted, depressed, counseling, drugs that will pillage, those few necessary substances pass from the conversion or taken from other organs, to ensure the survival of the body.

Nutritional damage

One of the key pinets of the mutation of the MTHFR gene is definitely the "nutritional damage". Diets on diets, drugs on drugs, foods and advice without first reading your own genetic mapping. It is since 2000 that this mutation is known, I leave it to you to imagine what damage has been done to the population, ignoring this problem but also for the total lack of knowledge on the part of those involved. How many unnecessary examinations, how many unsuccessful visits passed, how many useless, harmful drugs, how much economic waste, plundering our pockets and putting a strain on our mind. I understand this feeling, I know it very well, as Patient ZERO 1988.

Health and MTHFR

People present different problems and imbalances and with willpower knowing the truth given by genes in a natural way, only in this way can we face the path of physical and mental well-being. Different variations in genetic mutations and nutritional imbalances can cause serious health problems:

- Seizures
- Autism
- Increased risk of blood clots
- Cardiovascular disease
- Colon-rectal neoplasms
- Anxiety disorder MTHFR
- Death and memory loss
- Anxiety from depression and / or irritability
- Delays in development
- High or low homocysteine levels
- Hypertension
- Breast cancer risk
- Infertility or abortion
- Folate deficiency
- Neural tube defects and other birth defects
- Peripheral neuropathy
- Mass reduction or weight gain
- Schizophrenia
- ICT

10 plants as prevention and helpthrough mathematical nature

People with genetic mutations have a tendency to fall into serious, thankfully preventable diseases or at least bow a pejorative decorum and only Mother Nature can provide the appropriate answers and solutions using predictive Mathematics. Considered the involvement of different food shortages because of the missed conversions inherited, to combat and assist in the natural way, after years of studies and evaluations, such as "assistant professor in Patient Zero and 1990" I designed this Phytocomplex C10 prepared in the pharmacy fund, all natural, aims to help the various pressures and stress of life, toxicity, environmental, starting from the power supply, the substances that nourish life.

FitoComplex C10 - Galenic Phytoterpaic Remedy

Supporting actions of components

The various active ingredients in all plants help:

Immune system: counteracts viral infections, strengthens immune defenses. Immunomodulating. Counteracts forms of allergies of the respiratory system, asthma and tonsillitis, pharyngitis, otitis. Anti bacterial and deworming. Integration and functionality of cell membranes. Immunomodulating. Contrast tumor processes. Respiratory system: regulates the functions of the cardiovascular system. It helps the functionality of the early respiratory tract. Useful in cooling diseases, strengthens the immune system for children and adults. Nervous system: regulate stress, nervousness, tachycardia, sedative tonic, suitable genò for physical, mental fatigue. supports metabolism. Circulatory system: functionality of microcirculation, protector of capillaries, normalizes blood circulation. Digestive system: digestive, liver function, regularity of intestinal transit. Elimination of intestinal gases. Regularity of intestinal transit. Astringent action. Carbohydrate metabolism. Anti-inflammatory. Skeletal apparatus: remineralizing for bones. Useful for muscle pain, osteoarticular, rheumatism. Counteracts the trophism of the connective system.

Excretory apparatus: well-being and trophism of the mucous membranes and urinary tract. Diuretic, metabolic depurative. Anti-inflammatory, useful in urinary infections. Drainage of body fluids. Urinary tract functionality. Various systems and apparatus: hormonal, male and female balancer, aphrodisiac properties, useful skin, cellulite, wrinkles, nails, hair, spots, slows down aging. Contrast of cellulite imperfections. Purifying functions. Antioxidant of free radicals. Slimming action. Well-being of sight.

The various active ingredients in the whole plant: vitamins Group B, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin D, vitamin E. Mineral salts, iron, zinc, iodine, magnesium, iodine, magnesium, manganese, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, sulfur, phenols, aldehydes, idroiuglone, alkaloids, giucocinolati, tannins, acetic acid, lactones, nicotinic acid, riboflavin, carotenoids, flavonoids, malic acid, citric acid, oleic acid, pectin, organic acids, rubixantina, licopina, beta-carotene, anthocyanins, linoleic, arachidonic, sterols, phytosterols, glucosinolates, aromatic, isotiocinati, steroids, idroiuglone, giucocinolati. Amino acids serine, proline, serotonin, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, serine, glycine, histidine, threonine, cysteine, alanine, arginine, tyrosine, phenylalanine, valine, lysine, and arginine.

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